

Recommended citation: Ozkan, D., McNair, L. D., & Bairaktarova, D. (2018). Exploring practices of establishing and maintaining creative learning environments. In Clark, R., Munkebo Hussmann, P., Järvinen, H.-M., Murphy, M., & Etchells Vigild, M. (Eds.), *Creativity, Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineering Education Excellence. SEFI 46th Annual Conference* (pp. 349-356). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Brussels, Belgium. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14672562.

Exploring Practices of Establishing and Maintaining Creative Learning Environments

D. Ozkan¹

Graduate Research Assistant

E-mail: desenoz@vt.edu

L.D. McNair

Professor

E-mail: lmcnair@vt.edu

D. Bairaktarova

Assistant Professor

E-mail: dibairak@vt.edu

Department of Engineering Education
Virginia Tech
Blacksburg, VA, USA

Conference Key Areas: Teaching creativity & innovation; Innovation as the context for EE; Fostering entrepreneurship

Keywords: creativity, inclusivity, innovation

INTRODUCTION

In the last decade and more there has been a call for teaching creativity and critical thinking. Yet, while instructors find it to be very important, they are unsure of how to incorporate creative learning in undergraduate STEM curriculum [1]. Conflicts gravitate around efforts to both 'teach' creativity and to *foster environments* where creativity will 'naturally' flourish. This struggle signifies the discrepancy between a top-down and bottom-up teaching approach. With top-down instructional methods it is difficult to engender a sense of creative thinking in students; however, the other end of the spectrum appears as directionless learning, which can be unnerving to both instructors who have never taught (or been taught) in this manner as well as students who are accustomed to well-structured classrooms [2].

1 BACKGROUND

The most prevalent model in engineering education is a traditional learning environment that employs lecture-based instruction driven by standardized content. Coupled with tests that assess content competency, these educational practices largely suppress opportunities for creative development [3]. Yet there are still opportunities to shift ownership of content and its application from instructor to student and to thus provide students with more opportunities for original thinking [4]. When students gain confidence

in their learning ability early, they are more apt to engage in adaptive lifelong learning. With reduced structure in classrooms, students become more active in their own learning, which also enhances their understanding of new concepts. Moreover, with a more relaxed classroom environment, it is possible for tangential and emergent concepts to be explored, which creates avenues for interdisciplinarity [4].

Undergraduate classes are largely bound by the discipline in which they are housed, which makes potential connections across them difficult to discern. The application across disciplinary content is an avenue of creativity cultivation that is lost when disciplines are taught in isolation. With the integration across domain knowledge, students and faculty are better prepared for making connections in seemingly unrelated fields [5]. Moreover, in learning environments that facilitate cross-disciplinary work, collaboration is inherently flexible in that students and faculty working across domain spaces must incorporate a level of risk-tolerance and exploration that is less prevalent in traditional learning environments [7]. The difficulty in implementing interdisciplinarity in institutions involves the traditional disciplinary structures of higher education, which inhibit interdisciplinarity for students and faculty. The lack of alignment in faculty pursuit of interdisciplinarity and institutional values surfaces in “departments, budgets, and promotion and tenure” for traditional disciplines [2, p.375]. When faculty face such obstacles, undergraduate students are left without opportunities in class environments to engage in interdisciplinary learning.

The relationships between faculty and students are key in establishing and maintaining creative learning environments. Without avenues for faculty to engage in flexible learning environments and collaborate in the development of less traditional courses, they may lack the experience to engage students in environments in that they are less familiar [5]. In such environments, there is a need to become comfortable with discomfort as faculty and ultimately as students. Conventions of disciplinary assessment largely prevent students from seeing discomfort as a learning experience and more as a barrier to achieving high grades [4, 5]. For flexible learning environments to be effective in cultivating creativity, assessment practices are used best as ongoing practices that focus on student development rather than on their deliverables [8]. Through this study we seek to answer the following research question: *What practices do students, instructors, and facilitators employ to establish and maintain creative environments?*

2 METHODS

We gathered qualitative data by interviewing past and present faculty who have been involved in designing and facilitating courses required in a new program that focuses on innovation. The classes cover critical inquiry, ideation, and market feasibility, with all three classes including content, instructors and students from across disciplines. This study was aimed at answering questions regarding creative learning environments from the perspective of faculty and students.

2.1 Data Collection

We interviewed faculty involved in founding and developing each of the three courses in the program. We interviewed a total of six instructors and eight students. Class observations were gathered from one semester of the class focused on market feasibility. IRB approval has been obtained for this study.

The setting for this study comprised three undergraduate courses each required for an interdisciplinary minor in innovation. The first course, *Innovation in Context*, has been developed for students to learn how to critically analyze innovation and its ideals. The second course in the innovation minor, *Create!*, focuses on ideation and design thinking, in which students work in teams to find, define, and solve real-world problems that require students to engage in perspectives from multiple disciplines. Lastly, *The Startup Class* provides students more opportunities to work in interdisciplinary teams in the context of a modern innovation environment. Students begin to determine the feasibility of commercializing inventive technologies by working with inventors, entrepreneurs, advisors and other collaborators to ultimately take their work outside of the classroom. Each of these courses has been designed and delivered by faculty from different disciplines and is open to students from different majors.

2.3 Data Analysis

Interviews were audio-recorded and transcribed by a professional service and analyzed in conjunction with the course using qualitative coding software NVivo12. We analyzed the transcriptions as we interviewed participants to allow for follow-up questions that could provide a more complex perspective of emerging themes, which follows the method to “cycle back and forth” between the data analysis and collection to reduce blind spots [6, p.70]. We employed an iterative inductive coding strategy to identify emerging themes (Table 1) compared across faculty and student interviews until theoretical saturation.

With regard to limitations of the study, there are several improvements to be made. For instance, although a range of faculty were interviewed, the interviewed students were only from *The Startup Class*, which was in session at the time of the study; future studies will include students from all three courses as well as past students who have taken more than one class, beginning with *Create!* in Fall 2018. Another limitation is that because the innovation minor is new, there are few students who have fulfilled the minor requirements, making it difficult to gather longitudinal insights from their interdisciplinary experiences.

Table 1. Overview of High and Low-Level Codes

	<i>High Level Themes</i>	
	Course Design	Course Implementation
<i>Low Level Themes</i>	Course design is iterative	Focus on process
	Faculty with cross disciplinary backgrounds	Discomfort
	Pragmatism associated with course design	Flexibility in teaching
	Institutional Barriers	Working across disciplines
	Getting students to select the course	Assessment

3 FINDINGS

From the data analysis, we noted several themes in the context of the classroom environment that we grouped into course design and course implementation. These high and low-level themes will be described in further detail in the section below.

3.1 Course Design

When speaking to faculty about their courses, all who were involved in the design of the course referred to it in great length. They highlighted the iterative nature of these courses, and how each iteration was refined based on the past experiences. One of instructors noted that “things take time to develop, and there’s a lot of trial and error and almost administrative things that come out that you don’t think of.” The details of the course began to surface as instructors gained more experience in facilitating a course with more flexibility. From the interviews, we gathered that the faculty see the course design as an ongoing process that they “refine a little bit each year, each semester,” by seeking out feedback from other instructors in the minor and their assessment of students.

In addition, some of the courses have been taught by multiple instructors from different disciplines, which inevitably changes the course’s “flavor.” Faculty who co-taught a course mentioned “a pretty steep learning curve” based on the differences in disciplinary education. This learning curve could be another reason for maintaining the flexible learning environment, in which faculty and students alike are learning how to navigate a space that integrates disciplines. When the faculty teaching teams were larger, a graduate student acted as the point person for logistics to “make sure that the instructors are in the room a half hour before class starts working through issues.” This role of “herding cats” proved instrumental in ensuring that the instructors were able to contribute to the course development while also maintaining their accountability in their other responsibilities as tenure-track faculty. With a logistics coordinator providing the spine of the course, these faculty “subject experts” were able to improve upon an existing plan rather than having to create it all from scratch.

For the faculty designing and implementing the courses, several factors helped shape the first iterations. For *The Startup Class*, there was a grant that initiated the course but once the grant ended, faculty from industrial design and business listed two courses at the same time in the same classroom to have a cross-disciplinary course that would fulfill their teaching requirements. Their literal cross-listing posed problems with “restrictions and constraints in governance and regulation,” which have been gradually overcome as institutional shifts accompany the creation of the minor as part of the university’s new general education initiative. The *Innovation in Context* course was initially adapted by a graduate student from a graduate level course for the undergraduate level. The *Create!* class initially started alongside the founding of an institute on campus, in which the course was “engaging in the essence of the original intention, which was to engage students in this broader process” in the same sense that the institute was trying with faculty. Yet, when *Create!* “connected with business and startup,” “it took a shift” and “ideation” became more prominent in the syllabus. The department the courses are listed in as well as how they are titled has largely been determined by pragmatic collaboration and these decisions have also been largely affected by institutional barriers.

Even in the midst of a university shift toward interdisciplinarity, cross-disciplinary faculty who have led these classes encounter disciplinary boundaries. For faculty, these courses have been difficult to commit to because “no one gets department credit... but everyone commits time and resources to it.” For these commitments to be sustainable, there needs to be a shift in the value the institution places on courses that lay at the intersection of disciplines. This shift would also inform how students come to value interdisciplinarity and better explain why they choose to enroll in these courses.

Within a university with a large engineering population, courses that speak to innovation and business become largely populated by engineering students. For *Create!*, which started out as an honors course and has since been listed as an engineering course, “60-70%” of the students are in engineering. *The Startup Class* is cross-listed in engineering, business, and industrial design, which largely determines the students who choose to enroll. These numbers can sway, however, based on how and where the course is advertised or if it will count for a major requirement. In such cases, students will take the course to fulfill their major requirements. These reasons become important in the implementation of the course; according to one instructor, the course “takes on the flavor of the students,” and thus understanding which students enroll and their reasons can shed light on the effectiveness of the learning environment.

3.2 Course Implementation

From the faculty perspective, students have trouble navigating what is expected of them in a course that has more open-ended deliverables. For many faculty, students come in with the mindset of “tell me what I have to do and I’ll do it,” which is difficult to overcome in a short span of 15 weeks. Many of the instructors noted that the students wrestle with figuring out what the instructor wants before realizing that they “don’t want a perfect solution – a clean product.” These realizations are “reflected in their final presentations” and even in “their conversations they have within their group and across groups.” Getting students to focus more on the process than the product in design is a prominent goal across all the interviewed instructors. Specifically, for *The Startup Class*, one instructor noted that getting to a product or service was “icing on the cake”; learning “how to actually go out and talk to customers...ask good questions...make good hypotheses, and analyze the data” to then “refine the process all over again” was more important than the “icing.”

Yet, getting students to value the learning experience and the process involved a level of discomfort for them and the faculty guiding them through it. For many of the students, the combination of working in different disciplinary spaces and lack of “concrete objectives” caused confusion and struggle. In the *Create!* class, one instructor spoke of a “kind of shock” that students undergo when exposed to disciplines far outside of their own, as an example, guest lectures by professional artists. This shock was something the instructor “didn’t have the knowledge to coach [students] through” and had to unpack with the students, in ways that were uncomfortable for both parties. But by encouraging such a foreign type of navigation in the class, this instructor and students “co-constructed” the discomfort and worked through it rather than compartmentalizing or ignoring it altogether.

When speaking of institutional barriers, faculty expressed the pragmatism they needed to overcome administrative and governance challenges. However, in the actual class, several instructors spoke of their “ownership to tweak” the class “here and there,” while still being “careful to maintain what was proposed and approved through the engineering college.” Once “you’re acting responsibly within those bounds” of governance, “professors come to realize that [they have] pretty good control about what [they] do in [their] own classroom.” This flexibility was seen in the form of guests from across disciplines coming into courses to mentor and coach students in their projects. These guests helped “students get out of their ‘I’m a mechanical engineer’ or ‘I’m a marketing major’” conceptions to “help them realize that this stuff doesn’t exist in a vacuum.” Real-world instances of interdisciplinarity were shown to students through these

guests, such that students could begin to effectively navigate across disciplinary spaces by seeing the value of interdisciplinarity and integrating domain knowledge over 'divide and conquer' approaches in multidisciplinary work.

In these learning environments, students wrestled with cross-disciplinary spaces and shifting thought processes only towards the end of the semester, so consequently instructors had to also focus on their roles as facilitators in effectively coaching students through the discomfort. This manner of "unscripted teaching" necessitated a certain level of risk, in which it was possible for student groups to "go off the rails and ...not do so well." Yet, as a common theme across the courses, "there's something that happens in those last two or three weeks" when instructors note the "pivot in their thinking...and they've caught on." One instructor describes it as when students have "let go of uncertainty... and understand that [their project] doesn't have to be perfect." Yet, waiting for this point each semester can be difficult for newer, inexperienced instructors.

This theme of embracing uncertainty was prevalent, especially in the context of assessment. Student expectations heavily influenced how they navigated through course concepts: some perceived value that did not extend beyond that of an elective that is "set outside" of their discipline. There was a need to break pre-existing, often discipline-specific molds of assessment with which students came into the course. Students from *The Startup Class* from more technical backgrounds (e.g., engineering) "wished to have a little more direction," whereas those from business expressed an appreciation of the freedom. One student maintained that he "thrived on ambiguity" and described how he was often at odds with his engineering teammate. For instructors, these differences can be difficult to work through, but each interviewee focused on assessment as a formative process. The feedback students were given was ongoing and intended to "meet students where they are" and how "they are changing" throughout the semester. Instructors knew each of their students well and could discern how each was changing across the course.

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 Course Design

For each of the courses there are overt and covert notions of design that run through the course's content as well as in the manner by which faculty develop and implement them. The iterations help instructors determine what works in the classroom and what students need more guidance working through. Often faculty must also focus on the experience of implementing these courses, which can be difficult to be satisfied with, especially when students evaluate them with notions of finality. Moreover, the unscripted nature of these courses makes it difficult for faculty to pass on the courses to incoming instructors. Their past teaching experiences govern a lot of what is developed for future iterations, so for newer faculty picking up where more experienced faculty have left off can be a challenge. From the findings, it is clear that the system for passing the courses from instructor to instructor requires intentional guidance for an effective transition to take effect.

From an institutional standpoint, situating the courses in multiple departments and pushing through governance was a challenge. Faculty listed the same course multiple times in different departments so as to attract students from different disciplines and have multiple instructors leading the course. This display of creative pragmatism was common in the set-up of the course and speaks to the adaptability of the faculty to existing governmental structures. This adaptability also served faculty well when confronted with

different student expectations of the course. Each time a course was advertised differently or fulfilled a major requirement, a different set of students enrolled, each with different expectations that changed the dynamic of the course. For faculty this open-ended aspect of the course was challenging, but also added to the verve of course in that faculty were experiencing similar aspects of design that they then tried to instill in the students.

The sustainability of such courses can be difficult to maintain when institutional barriers limit which faculty can take on a course design or instructor role. In courses without a graduate student “cat herder,” establishing a common language among faculty was a recurring challenge, which mirrored that of the cross-disciplinary students tasked with working together. In the courses that were co-taught, faculty experienced similar struggles as the students. This mirroring effect seemed to put faculty in the position of unpacking their own experiences, to then be able to turn the learning experiences into role-modeling and coaching opportunities for students experiencing similar issues. Moreover, there was a certain institutional value placed on the different disciplines when students from different disciplines had mentors from their discipline. In course offerings that involved faculty solely from engineering or business, there may have been a perceived difference in the value that students with majors outside of these could supply. Hints of this sentiment were conveyed by non-engineering students in *The Startup Class*, when they spoke of the heavy technical focus that seemed to drive the course.

The expectations that students bring into each course largely changes the flavor of each offering, and understanding them can be a learning curve in itself for less-experienced faculty. For students who take the class to fulfill a requirement or for students who come in with a startup idea that they plan to pursue post-graduation, there is a vast difference in what each will take out of it. Moreover, these differences can negatively affect how they engage with the material. For instance, the student trying to commercialize their idea comes in focused on the product they have envisioned, seeking to acquire a different set of skills than the student taking the class to fulfill a requirement. There is a clear need to begin the class with an exploration of who the students are such that instructors can adapt to the diversity of disciplines, values, and expectations.

4.2 Course Implementation

In the instruction and facilitation of the course, much of the struggle faculty had was getting students to focus on the process rather than finished products. Students coming out of the majority of K-12 systems as well many undergraduate courses learn the value of grades and deliverables. With these courses, faculty were challenged in dispelling notions that a perfect product would earn students the top results. However, for a 15-week semester class, these pre-existing notions of assessment were difficult to work through. Moreover, even when and if they were overcome, subsequent classes may still foreground the importance of grades through ironclad assessment rubrics.

As these three courses become more established in the institution and known to students in their relation to one another, the issue of time that all the faculty have pointed out might become less of a constraint. In the current model, where students do not pass through each of the courses, there is a notable transition period in which they have to overcome their expectations and begin to realize that “perfect solutions” are not the goal of the course. This shift to focus on the process takes time, but because it is an underlying theme across the courses, many of the current challenges may be mitigated when students take all three of the classes that comprise the minor. Still, conventions of design

focus on products and solutions. To get students to shift their focus to the process requires a certain level of discomfort and trust in their peers and their instructor to ultimately “let go of the uncertainty” as one professor described.

Discomfort plays a major role in cultivating creativity, for when faculty and students become comfortable navigating through discomfort, they learn to engage in processes that they may have shied away from in the past [5]. Contrary to the creative pragmatism employed by faculty in developing and situating their courses within the institution, the flexibility in the classroom has allowed for faculty to take ownership and control of their class environments. Yet, institutional barriers that must be overcome for interdisciplinary courses to supply credit to faculty instructors is a taxing experience and may inhibit the permanence of the minor’s mission. The misalignment between the institutional and course values acts as a recurring challenge that may ultimately tire faculty involved in the minor [2, p. 375]. Moreover, when interdisciplinarity is not overtly valued by the institution, undergraduate conceptions are handicapped at the start.

5 SUMMARY

The creativity of faculty in designing and implementing these courses is clear from how they have valued the process by refining and iterating the course. Stemming from flexibility and pragmatism, the traditional learning manner of instructor to student information transfer is transformed in these environments in which instructors and students learn from each other by maintaining a learning environment that values the process over the product. Future work will situate this study within current literature on creative engineering education pedagogies, with particular focus on project/problem-based learning, which foregrounds similar values.

REFERENCES

- [1] Coate, K., & Boulos, A. (2012). Creativity in education: Challenging the assumptions. *London Review of Education* (Vol. 10).
- [2] McNair, L. D., Newswander, C., Boden, D. and Borrego, M. “Student and faculty interdisciplinary identities in self-managed teams,” *Journal of Engineering Education*, vol. 100, no. 2, pp. 374–396, 2011.
- [3] Shaheen, R. (2010). Creativity and Education. *Creative Education*, 1(3), 166–169.
- [4] Davies, D., Jindal-Snape, D., Collier, C., Digby, R., Hay, P., & Howe, A. (2013). Creative learning environments in education—A systematic literature review. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 8, 80-91.
- [5] Collard, P., & Looney, J. (2014). Nurturing creativity in education. *European Journal of Education*, 49(3), 348–364.
- [6] Miles, M. Huberman, M. and Saldana, J. “Fundamentals of Qualitative Data Analysis,” in *Qualitative Data Analysis - A Methods Sourcebook*, 2014, 69–103.
- [7] Bairaktarova, D. and Eodice, M. (2017). *Creative Ways of Knowing in Engineering*. Berlin: Springer.
- [8] Bairaktarova, D. (2017). The New Renaissance Artificers: Harnessing Creativity in the Engineering Classroom. In *Creative Ways of Knowing in Engineering*. Eds: Bairaktarova, D. and Eodice, M. Berlin: Springer.